

FUNCTIONAL VASCULAR PROGRAMMING IN YOUNG RATS: CONSEQUENCES OF EXPOSURE TO REPEATED MATERNAL IMMOBILIZATION STRESS DURING LATE GESTATION

Programação Funcional Vascular em Ratos Jovens: Consequências da Exposição ao Estresse Materno por Imobilização Repetida no Final da Gestação

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ABSTRACT

Prenatal exposure to chronic gestational stress provides a valuable experimental framework for examining early transgenerational effects, including significant repercussions on the cardiovascular system of the young offspring. Particular attention has been directed toward the modulation of catecholamine-mediated vasoconstriction and endothelium-dependent relaxation prior to the emergence of compensatory mechanisms in adulthood or the development of overt structural alterations. The present study aimed to investigate the effects of repeated (chronic) maternal immobilization stress during late gestation (Str) on vascular reactivity in young *Wistar* rat offspring. Vascular function was assessed in isolated aortic rings with and without endothelium by constructing concentration–effect curves to norepinephrine, acetylcholine, and sodium nitroprusside, in the presence or absence of specific pharmacological inhibitors. The contribution of α 1D- and α 1B-adrenergic receptors, as well as calcium-dependent mechanisms, to these responses was also examined. In parallel, systolic blood pressure, morphological characteristics of the heart and adrenal glands, and plasma corticosterone levels were determined. The results demonstrate that Str alters vascular responsiveness to norepinephrine and acetylcholine, with these effects being dependent on endothelial integrity. Moreover, Str was associated with increased systolic blood pressure, altered plasma corticosterone levels, and increased adrenal gland weight, without detectable morphological changes in the heart. Collectively, these findings indicate that prenatal stress exposure during the final week of gestation induces early functional vascular alterations associated with activation of the hypothalamic–pituitary–adrenal axis and the initial development of a hypertensive phenotype in young rats.

Keywords: Chronic gestational stress, Fetal cardiovascular programming, Endothelium, Aortic reactivity, Early prohypertensive phenotype.

RESUMO

A exposição pré-natal ao estresse gestacional crônico permite avaliar seus efeitos transgeracionais precoces, incluindo repercussões relevantes sobre o sistema cardiovascular da prole jovem com especial ênfase na modulação da vasoconstrição mediada por catecolaminas e no relaxamento dependente do endotélio antes do desenvolvimento de mecanismos compensatórios na vida adulta ou do aparecimento de alterações estruturais evidentes. O objetivo do presente estudo foi investigar os efeitos do estresse repetido (crônico) de imobilização materna no final da gestação (Str) sobre a reatividade vascular em filhotes jovens de ratos *Wistar*. A função vascular desses animais foi avaliada em anéis de aorta com e sem endotélio por meio de curvas concentração-efeito à noradrenalina, acetilcolina e ao nitroprussiato de sódio, na presença ou ausência de diferentes inibidores. O envolvimento dos receptores α 1D e α 1B-adrenérgicos e do cálcio nessas respostas também foi investigado. Paralelamente, foram analisadas a pressão arterial sistólica, as características morfológicas do coração e das glândulas adrenais, bem como os níveis plasmáticos de corticosterona. Os resultados do presente trabalho mostram que o Str altera a reatividade de à noradrenalina e à acetilcolina, sendo esses efeitos dependentes da integridade do endotélio. Além disso, o Str implica elevação da pressão arterial sistólica, alterações nos níveis plasmáticos de corticosterona e no peso das glândulas adrenais sem alterações morfológicas cardíacas. Em conjunto, esses achados indicam que a exposição ao estresse pré-natal durante a última semana de gestação promove alterações vasculares funcionais precoces associadas à ativação do eixo hipotálamo-hipófise-adrenal e ao desenvolvimento inicial de um fenótipo hipertensivo em ratos na idade jovem.

Palavras-chave: Estresse gestacional crônico, Programação fetal cardiovascular, Endotélio, Reatividade aórtica, Fenótipo pró-hipertensivo precoce.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Stress is a complex, multifactorial phenomenon arising from the intensity, frequency, duration, and type of stressors (McEwen, 2012). Adaptation is primarily mediated by the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis and sympathetic nervous system (SNS), driving systemic release of glucocorticoids and catecholamines that induce hemodynamic and metabolic changes (Lopes *et al.*, 2021; Deussing, 2021; Menard, 2016; Nicolaidis *et al.*, 2021). Prenatal maternal stress in rats, via repeated immobilization, alters β -adrenergic receptor expression in the offspring's left ventricle, changes linked to cardiovascular disease (Jevjdovic *et al.*, 2019). Daily 1-hour immobilization during late gestation chronically activates maternal HPA function, elevating corticosterone and programming offspring vascular responses, including enhanced pressor reactivity and neuropeptide Y-mediated aortic sensitivity (Igosheva *et al.*, 2007). This model reliably induces persistent endothelial dysfunction, with reduced NO-dependent vasodilation and heightened sympathetic contractility, offering a pharmacology-free approach to study programmed hypertension (Emack, 2008). The present study evaluated aortic reactivity in 30-day-old male offspring exposed to prenatal stress, focusing on vascular alterations, NO- and Ca^{2+} -dependent responses, and α_1 -adrenergic receptor function. Specific pharmacological inhibitors were used to dissect the contributions of these pathways.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Animals

Female *Wistar* rats were obtained from the Animal Facility of the Faculty of Health Sciences, Federal University of Grande Dourados (UFGD), Brazil. They were housed four per cage under standard conditions (12-h light/dark cycle starting at 6:00 a.m., 23 ± 3 °C, $60 \pm 5\%$ humidity) with ad libitum access to chow and water. All procedures followed the National Research Council's Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals (1996) and were approved by UFGD's Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee (protocol no. 04/2016–CEUA).

2.2 Estrous Cycle Monitoring, Mating and Pregnancy Confirmation

In adult rats of the strain used in this study, the estrous cycle lasts 4 to 5 days. Estrous cycle monitoring was initiated on day 63 of age for each animal. Vaginal mucosal cells were collected at the same time each day for 15 consecutive days. Samples were smeared onto glass slides, moistened with a drop of saline, and examined under a light microscope to determine the stage of the estrous

cycle. Four 12-week-old, nulliparous females in estrus were paired with two fertile males overnight. The next morning, males were removed, and vaginal smears were collected with saline-moistened cotton, avoiding cervical stimulation. Pregnancy was confirmed by the presence of sperm in the smear and by the identification of estrus, designated as the first gestational day. Pregnant females were then individually housed.

2.3 Stress Induction

One group of pregnant rats completed the entire gestational period without exposure to any stress protocol; the offspring from these dams constituted the control group (C). Another group of pregnant rats was subjected to repeated immobilization stress according to the method described by Ely et al. (1997). Animals were restrained for 1 hour per day for seven consecutive days, always at the same time of day (between 9:00 and 10:00 a.m.), beginning on gestational day 12. This period coincides with critical stages of neurodevelopment, including the formation of structures such as the thalamus and hypothalamus (Rice and Barone, 2000; Barone *et al.*, 2000). The offspring from these dams were designated as the prenatal repeated immobilization stress group (Str).

2.4 Weaning

Litter size was standardized to eight pups per dam, prioritizing males. Offspring were weaned on postnatal day 22 and housed four per cage until 4 weeks of age (\approx 65–80 g) for experiments. Female pups were kept only to maintain litter size and used in a separate study.

2.5 Blood Sample Collection

After the establishment of each experimental group, animals were euthanized by CO₂ inhalation followed by exsanguination via puncture of the inferior vena cava. Blood samples were collected into heparinized syringes and centrifuged (3.500 rpm, 10 min, 4°C) to obtain plasma. The plasma samples were subsequently stored at -80°C until further analysis.

2.6 Cardiac and adrenal assessment, systolic blood pressure and plasma corticosterone

Immediately after euthanasia, adrenal glands and the left ventricle (LV) were excised, cleared of surrounding tissue, and weighed. LV hypertrophy was evaluated using the LV mass-to-tibial length ratio and, via echocardiography, the LV mass-to-body weight ratio, allowing correlation between *in vivo* and postmortem measurements (Yin *et al.*, 1982). Systolic blood pressure (SBP) was measured via noninvasive tail-cuff plethysmography (Narco BioSystems®, Austin, TX, USA), averaging two consecutive readings. After 12-15 h fasting, animals were anesthetized (pentobarbital 50 mg/kg, *i.p.*) and decapitated. Blood was collected in heparinized tubes, centrifuged (3.000 × g, 15 min, 4°C), and

plasma stored at -80°C for corticosterone determination by radioimmunoassay (Coat-A-Count Rat Corticosterone kit, Diagnostic Products Corporation).

2.7 Vascular Reactivity

Descending thoracic aortas were excised, cleaned, and cut into ~ 4 mm rings, then mounted in organ baths (Ugo Basile myograph) under 1.5 g resting tension. Rings equilibrated for 1 h in Krebs–Henseleit solution (37°C , pH 7.4) bubbled with carbogen (95% O_2 /5% CO_2). One ring per pair retained intact endothelium (+E), while the other was denuded (–E). Endothelial integrity was confirmed by acetylcholine (10^{-4} M) induced relaxation after phenylephrine (10^{-5} M) precontraction ($>70\%$ relaxation = intact; $<5\%$ = removed). Concentration-response curves (CRCs) to KCl (80 mM) and noradrenaline (NA, 10^{-10} to 10^{-5} M) were generated in aortic rings. NA was tested under control conditions or following 30-min incubation with L-NAME (3×10^{-4} M, NOS inhibitor), indomethacin (INDO; 10^{-5} M, non-selective COX inhibitor), prazosin (10^{-8} M, non-selective α_1 antagonist), or WB-4101 (2-[[[2-(2,6-dimethoxyphenoxy)ethyl]amino]methyl]-1,4-benzodioxane; 10^{-8} M, selective α_{1A}/α_{1B} antagonist) to dissect NO-dependent, prostanoid-mediated, and α_{1D}/α_{1B} -mediated components of vascular reactivity. Additional CRCs were obtained for acetylcholine (+E) and sodium nitroprusside (SNP) in +E or -E rings after submaximal NA precontraction (10^{-6} - 10^{-5} M), applying cumulative agonist concentrations (10^{-13} – 10^{-4} M) every 2-3 min until plateau. Relaxation was expressed as a percentage of NA-induced precontraction. All reagents were from Sigma Chemical Co. (St. Louis, MO, USA).

2.8 Contribution of Intracellular and Extracellular Ca^{2+}

To assess intracellular vs. extracellular Ca^{2+} in NA-induced contraction, endothelium-denuded aortic rings were initially incubated 1 min in Ca^{2+} -free Krebs and stimulated with NA (10^{-7} – 10^{-6} M) to record contractile force. Extracellular Ca^{2+} contribution was then evaluated via cumulative CaCl_2 additions in the presence of NA. Intracellular stores were depleted by incubating rings in Ca^{2+} -free Krebs with EDTA (1 mM) plus NA (10^{-4} M), followed by washes in Ca^{2+} -free Krebs with NA, repeated until no further contraction occurred, indicating complete intracellular Ca^{2+} depletion.

2.9 Statistical analysis

Data are presented as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM). Comparisons between groups for cardiac mass, adrenal hypertrophy, plasma corticosterone levels, and final SBP were performed using Student's t test followed by Tukey's post hoc test, using GraphPad Prism version 6.04. Individual concentration–effect curves were fitted by nonlinear regression, and comparisons of EC_{50}

values and maximal responses were performed using either Student's t test or analysis of variance (ANOVA), as appropriate. A P value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Assessment of Cardiac and Adrenal Hypertrophy and Plasma Corticosterone

Rats exposed to prenatal repeated immobilization stress (Str) did not exhibit any signs of left ventricular hypertrophy compared to control animals (C), as evidenced by the left ventricle-to-tibia ratio [LV (g)/tibia (mm); C: 0.13 ± 0.06 vs. Str: 0.15 ± 0.08] and by echocardiographic measurements [LV (g)/final body weight (g); C: 1.25 ± 0.11 vs. Str: 1.43 ± 0.17]. However, classical adrenal hypertrophy was observed, characterized by a significant increase in the dry weight of the adrenal glands (C: 0.51 ± 0.05 vs. Str: $0.81 \pm 0.03^*$, $P < 0.05$). In addition, exposure to repeated immobilization stress resulted in elevated systolic blood pressure [SBP: C = 115.8 ± 14.7 vs. Str = $150.1 \pm 8.47^*$ mmHg] and increased plasma corticosterone levels [C = 47.8 ± 11.7 vs. Str = $99.4 \pm 14.1^*$ ng/mL], with $P < 0.05$.

3.2 Vascular Reactivity

3.2.1 Effects of prenatal repeated immobilization stress on vascular responses to noradrenaline in the presence or absence of pharmacological inhibitors

Prenatal repeated immobilization stress reduced the maximal response and decreased sensitivity to norepinephrine in endothelium-intact rings (+E) compared to the control group. This effect was abolished by pre-incubation with L-NAME and by mechanical removal of the endothelium, but it was not affected by pre-incubation with indomethacin. No statistically significant differences were observed in the reactivity of endothelium-denuded rings (-E) across all experimental groups (Figure 1; Tables 1 and 2).

Figure 1: Concentration-effect curves of noradrenaline obtained in thoracic aortic rings with (A) and without endothelium (B) isolated from *Wistar* rats exposed or not to prenatal stress

C: control group; Str: prenatal stress induced by repeated immobilization. L-NAME: preincubation (60 min) with $N\omega$ -nitro-L-arginine methyl ester (3×10^{-4} M); INDO: preincubation (60 min) with indomethacin (10^{-5} M). Data are presented as mean \pm SEM. Number of animals: 6–8 rats per experimental group.

Source: Research data (2017).

Table 1: Mean values of the maximum response in the concentration-effect curves, in the presence or absence of inhibitors, obtained in aortic rings with (+E) and without (-E) endothelium, from the same thoracic aorta, isolated from *Wistar* rats exposed or not to prenatal stress.

GROUPS	¹ MAXIMUM RESPONSE Tension (g)	
	(+E)	(-E)
C	2.45 \pm 0.21	3.52 \pm 0.40*
C + INDO	2.50 \pm 0.35	3.59 \pm 0.33*
C + L-NAME	3.50 \pm 0.70 [#]	3.56 \pm 0.11* [#]
Str	1.10 \pm 0.40 ^S	3.57 \pm 0.72*
Str + INDO	1.15 \pm 0.40 ^S	3.53 \pm 0.63*
Str + L-NAME	3.58 \pm 0.55 [#]	3.61 \pm 0.55* [#]

C: control group; Str: prenatal stress (repeated immobilization). L-NAME: preincubation (60 min) with $N\omega$ -nitro-L-arginine methyl ester (3×10^{-4} M); INDO: preincubation (60 min) with indomethacin (10^{-5} M). Values are mean \pm SEM (n = 6–8 per group). [#]P < 0.05 vs. (+E) rings without L-NAME. [#]P < 0.05 vs. (+E) rings from the control group, with or without L-NAME and INDO. *P < 0.05 vs. corresponding (+E) preparations. *[#]P > 0.05 vs. corresponding (+E) preparations from control and stressed groups in the presence of L-NAME.

Source: Research data (2017).

Table 2: Effective concentration 50% (EC50) in concentration-effect curves, in the presence or absence of inhibitors, obtained in aortic rings with (+E) and without (-E) endothelium, from the same thoracic aorta, isolated from *Wistar* rats exposed or not to prenatal stress.

GROUPS	¹ EC50 ($\times 10^{-8}$ M)	
	(+E)	(-E)
C	4.05 (1.65-5.17)	0.63 ^S (1.11-2.01)
C+ INDO	3.99 (1.77-5.56)	0.66 ^S (1.28-1.99)
C + L-NAME	0.67* (1.54-4.23)	0.59 ^{S*} (0.99-2.04)
Str	8.05 [#] (0.99-12.14)	0.64 ^S (1.56-2.41)
Str + INDO	7.99 [#]	0.61 ^S

	(1.47-4.99)	(1.39-2.08)
Str + L-NAME	0.59*	0.60 ^{S*}
	(1.87-4.62)	(1.14-1.95)

C: control; Str: prenatal stress (repeated immobilization). Values are mean ± 95% CI of EC₅₀ (n = 6–8). L-NAME: 60 min preincubation with N ω -nitro-L-arginine methyl ester (3×10^{-4} M); INDO: 60 min preincubation with indomethacin (10^{-5} M). *P < 0.05 vs. (+E) rings without L-NAME; #P < 0.05 vs. (+E) control rings ± L-NAME/INDO; ^SP < 0.05 vs. corresponding (+E) rings; ^{S*}P > 0.05 vs. (+E) rings with L-NAME in both groups.

Source: Research data (2017).

3.2.2 Effects of Prenatal Stress by Repeated Immobilization on Receptor-Independent KCl-Induced Contraction

Prenatal stress induced by repeated immobilization attenuated the maximal contractile response to KCl without affecting the EC₅₀ in either endothelium-intact (+E) or endothelium-denuded (-E) aortic rings (Figure 2, Table 3).

Figure 2: Concentration-effect curves for KCl obtained in thoracic aortic rings with (A) and without endothelium (B) isolated from *Wistar* rats exposed or not to prenatal stress.

C: control group; Str: group exposed to prenatal stress by repeated immobilization. Data presented as mean ± SEM. Number of animals: 6-8 rats in each experimental group.

Source: Research data (2017).

Table 3: Mean values of the maximum response and the 50% effective concentration (EC₅₀) in concentration-effect curves to KCl, obtained in aortic rings with and without endothelium, from the same thoracic aorta, isolated from *Wistar* rats exposed or not to prenatal stress

GROUPS	PARAMETERS			
	¹ MAXIMUM RESPONSE		² EC ₅₀ (x10 ⁻⁸ M)	
	Tension (g)		(+E)	(-E)
C	(+E) 1.92± 0.21	(-E) 1.96± 0.73	0.43 (1.27-9.7)	0.38 (1.39-1.92)
Str	1.34± 0.15*	1.29± 0.28*	0.51 (1.12-12.14)	0.47 (0.9-10.28)

C: control group; Str: group exposed to prenatal stress by repeated immobilization. ¹Values presented as mean ± standard error of the mean (SEM). ²Values presented as mean ± 95% confidence interval of CE₅₀. Number of animals: 6-8 rats in each experimental group. *P<0.05 C vs Str.

Source: Research data (2017).

3.2.3 Assessment of α_1 -Adrenergic Receptor Involvement in the Contractile Response to Noradrenaline

Prazosin (PRAZ), a reversible competitive antagonist of α_1 -adrenergic receptors, and WB-4101, a reversible competitive antagonist of α_1B/A -adrenergic receptors, were used to evaluate the contribution of vascular smooth muscle α_1 -adrenergic receptor signaling to the contractile response in aortic rings. In endothelium-free preparations, both PRAZ and WB-4101 produced a rightward shift in the noradrenaline concentration-response curve of similar magnitude in the control (C) and prenatal stress (Str) groups (Figure 3, Table 4).

Figure 3: Concentration-effect curves of noradrenaline obtained in aortic rings without endothelium, in the presence or absence of prazosin 10^{-8} M (A), or WB-4101 (B) isolated from *Wistar* rats exposed or not to prenatal stress.

C: control group; Str: group exposed to prenatal stress by repeated immobilization. PRAZ: prazosin 10^{-8} M; WB-4101: 2-[[[2-(2,6-dimethoxyphenoxy)ethyl]amino]methyl]-1,4-benzodioxane; 10^{-8} M. Data presented as mean \pm SEM. Number of animals: 6-8 rats in each experimental group. *P < 0.05.

Source: Research data (2017).

Table 4: EC₅₀ values from concentration-effect curves obtained in endothelium-denuded aortic rings from *Wistar* rats exposed or not to prenatal stress, in the absence or presence of prazosin (10^{-8} M) or WB-4101 (10^{-8} M).

GROUPS	¹ EC ₅₀ (x10 ⁻⁸ M)
C	0.59 (1.11-2.01)
C + PRAZ	9.04 ^{*#} (2.03-12.14)
C + WB-4101	10.92 ^{*#} (3.12-10.09)
Str	0.61 (1.30-1.78)
Str + PRAZ	9.19 ^{*#} (5.67-6.14)
Str + WB-4101	11.01 ^{*#} (4.31-5.73)

C: control group; Str: group exposed to prenatal stress induced by repeated immobilization. PRAZ: prazosin (10^{-8} M); WB-4101: 2-[[[2-(2,6-dimethoxyphenoxy)ethyl]amino]methyl]-1,4-benzodioxane (10^{-8} M). Values are expressed as mean \pm 95% confidence interval of the EC₅₀. Number of animals: 6-8 rats per experimental group. *P < 0.05 compared with preparations in the absence of PRAZ, and in the absence WB-4101. [#]P > 0.05 for comparisons among C+PRAZ vs C+WB-4101; C+PRAZ vs Str+PRAZ; C+PRAZ vs Str+WB-4101; and Str+PRAZ vs Str+WB-4101.

Source: Research data (2017).

3.2.4 Vascular Relaxation to Acetylcholine and Sodium Nitroprusside

Prenatal immobilization stress increased both maximal relaxation and sensitivity to acetylcholine in endothelium-intact aortic rings (Figure 4A, Table 5). In addition, the concentration–response curve to the nitric oxide donor sodium nitroprusside (SNP) was left-shifted in aortic rings with or without endothelium from stressed rats, without altering the maximal response (Figure 4B, Table 6).

Figure 4: Concentration-effect curves to acetylcholine (A) and sodium nitroprusside (B) obtained in thoracic aortic rings with (+E) and without endothelium (-E) isolated from *Wistar* rats exposed or not to prenatal stress.

C: control group; Str: group exposed to prenatal stress by repeated immobilization. Data presented as mean ± SEM. Number of animals: 6-8 rats in each experimental group. *P < 0.05.

Source: Research data (2017).

Table 5: Mean values of maximum response and 50% effective concentration (EC50) in concentration-effect curves to acetylcholine obtained in endothelial aortic rings with endothelium isolated from *Wistar* rats exposed or not to prenatal stress.

GROUPS	PARAMETERS	
	¹ Maximum relaxation (%) induced by ACh	² EC50 (x10 ⁻⁸ M)
C	65.7 ± 0.21	7.2 (6.6-7.8)
Str	89.4 ± 0.93*	6.1* (1.12-11.08)

C: control group; Str: group exposed to prenatal stress by repeated immobilization. ¹Values presented as mean ± SEM of the % relaxation relative to the contraction prior to NA. ²Values presented as mean ± 95% confidence interval of CE₅₀. Number of animals: 6-8 rats in each experimental group. *P < 0.05 C vs Str.

Source: Research data (2017).

Table 6: Mean values of maximum response and 50% effective concentration (EC50) in concentration-effect curves to sodium nitroprusside obtained in aortic rings with (+E) and without endothelium (-E) isolated from *Wistar* rats exposed or not to prenatal stress.

GROUPS	PARAMETERS			
	¹ Maximum relaxation (%) induced by SNP		² EC50(x10 ⁻⁹ M)	
	+E	-E	+E	-E
C	98.09 ± 1.9	97.99 ± 6.7	3.1 (2.3-4.0)	3.4 (3.6-5.2)
Str	99.76 ± 5,3	98.45 ± 8.1	5.77* (3.9-8.0)	6.07* (3.5-7.4)

C: control group; Str: group exposed to prenatal stress by repeated immobilization. ¹Values presented as mean ± SEM of the % relaxation relative to the contraction prior to NA. ²Values presented as mean ± 95% confidence interval of CE₅₀. Number of animals: 6-8 rats in each experimental group. *P<0.05 C vs Str.

Source: Research data (2017).

3.2.5 Noradrenaline-Induced Contraction in Calcium-Free Medium and Calcium Chloride Vascular Reactivity

Prenatal stress induced by repeated immobilization reduced the contractile response to noradrenaline in Ca²⁺-free Krebs solution (Figure 5A, Table 7). Furthermore, concentration-response curves to CaCl₂, in the presence of noradrenaline, in endothelium-denuded aortic rings from these animals exhibited a decreased maximal response. No changes in agonist sensitivity, as assessed by pD₂ values, were observed (Figure 5B, Table 7).

Figure 5: Contractile response to noradrenaline in endothelium-denuded rat aortic rings in Ca²⁺-free Krebs solution (A) and concentration-response curves to CaCl₂ (B).

C: control group; Str: group exposed to prenatal stress by repeated immobilization. Data presented as mean ± SEM. Number of animals: 6-8 rats in each experimental group. *P < 0.05 C vs Str.

Source: Research data (2017).

Table 7: Mean values of maximum response and 50% effective concentration (EC50) in concentration-effect curves to CaCl₂ obtained in aortic rings without endothelium (-E) isolated from *Wistar* rats exposed or not to prenatal stress.

GROUPS	PARAMETERS	
	¹ Maximum Response	² CE50 (x10 ⁻⁸ M)
C	2.70 ± 0.43	7.99 (5.2-11.71)
Str	1.99 ± 0.54*	8.08 (4.43-9.08)

C: control group; Str: group exposed to prenatal stress by repeated immobilization. ¹Values presented as mean ± standard error of the mean (SEM). ²Values presented as mean ± 95% confidence interval of CE₅₀. Number of animals: 6-8 rats in each experimental group. *P<0.05 C vs Str.

Source: Research data (2017).

4 DISCUSSION

In this study, exposure to chronic prenatal stress was associated with increased adrenal gland dry weight and elevated plasma corticosterone levels, indicating sustained activation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis. This pattern reflects an adaptive neuroendocrine response to chronic stress, as widely described in experimental models (Nunez *et al.*, 2025; Vellapandian, 2024; Knezevic *et al.*, 2023; Borrow *et al.*, 2019). From a cardiovascular perspective, repeated stress may contribute to arterial hypertension through modulation of multiple regulatory systems, including the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone axis and increased release of cortisol and catecholamines from the adrenal glands (Ritter *et al.*, 2025; Matthews *et al.*, 2004; Kulkarni *et al.*, 1998). Consistent with this, prenatal immobilization stress induced elevated blood pressure in our model, likely linked to enhanced adrenal activity, as supported by increased adrenal mass and sympathetic stimulation. Beyond systemic effects, prenatal stress also directly modulated vascular function. Aortic rings from stressed animals displayed hyporesponsiveness to norepinephrine and hyperresponsiveness to acetylcholine, both dependent on endothelial integrity. Pre-incubation with a NOS inhibitor, but not a COX inhibitor, abolished the observed differences in norepinephrine-induced contraction, while acetylcholine-induced vasodilation was enhanced, indicating that NO, rather than prostanoids, mediates these changes (Bernatova *et al.*, 2018; Lanza-Júnior & Cordellini, 2007; Nadaud *et al.*, 1996). Additionally, increased sensitivity of vascular smooth muscle to exogenous NO (SNP) in endothelium-denuded rings suggests enhanced effector responsiveness, complementing potential endothelial alterations. When investigating adrenergic signaling, selective antagonism of α 1-adrenergic receptors (α 1D, α 1B, and α 1A), which are predominant in the vascular smooth muscle of the aorta of *Wistar* rats, did not affect vascular responses. This implies that the reduction in contractility induced by norepinephrine is not due to changes at the receptor level, but

rather to mechanisms such as increased endothelial NO production (Lanza-Júnior & Cordellini, 2007; Cordellini *et al.*, 2006) and activation of the α 2-adrenergic receptor in the endothelium (Rascado *et al.*, 2005). KCl-induced contraction, independent of receptor activation, was also reduced, supporting involvement of intracellular mediators regulating smooth muscle contractility (Chang *et al.*, 2002). Intracellular Ca^{2+} homeostasis plays a central role in vascular tone. Stressed animals exhibited reduced contractile responses to norepinephrine, suggesting altered intracellular Ca^{2+} mobilization, potentially via impaired IP_3 -mediated release from the endoplasmic reticulum or reduced Ca^{2+} stores. Additionally, attenuated Ca^{2+} influx through voltage-dependent channels, particularly L-type channels, may contribute, as supported by Ca^{2+} concentration-response curves in endothelium-denuded rings (Berridge *et al.*, 2003; Nelson *et al.*, 1988; Godfraind *et al.*, 1986; Luo *et al.*, 2008).

5 FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The final stage of gestation represents a critical window of vulnerability during which maternal stress can reprogram offspring blood pressure regulation. The hypertensive phenotype observed in young rats is closely associated with adrenal endocrine activation, yet it is partially mitigated by endothelial-mediated vascular plasticity, which attenuates peripheral contractile responses. These functional alterations precede any cardiac remodeling, underscoring the significance of identifying early indicators of cardiovascular risk. Collectively, these considerations emphasize the gestational environment as a key determinant of long-term vascular health and illustrate that modulation of arterial tone constitutes one of the earliest adaptive responses to prenatal stress.

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